

Dr David Gerber Discusses Common Pelvic Floor Issues

Pelvic floor problems are common, but they can be easily treated. In addition to maintaining bladder and bowel control, sexual function, and keeping the pelvic organs in their proper positions, the pelvic floor acts as a "home" for the pelvic organs, including the urinary bladder, rectum, and vagina.

There are, however, pelvic floor disorders that can occur. The most common problems include urinary problems, loss of pelvic organ support, and pelvic organ prolapse. One of the main causes of pelvic floor dysfunction is childbirth, and the risk increases with the number of children a woman has. Overweight or obesity, genetic predisposition, and aging changes are also risk factors.

According to Dr David Gerber, MD, a [specialist in labiaplasty and reconstructive surgery with Meridia Medical in Toronto](#), pelvic floor disorders are fairly common. It is estimated that 10 to 50 percent of women report urinary leakage, and 50 percent of women who have had children develop prolapse. Furthermore, 20 percent of women will undergo surgery for pelvic organ prolapse or urinary incontinence in their lifetime."

Unfortunately, many women let these issues affect their daily lives for years before seeking treatment. There are many people who fear having an accident if they cough or sneeze in public, or who avoid social situations because of urgency or incontinence. However, many pelvic floor issues can be treated easily.

Stress incontinence is a common pelvic floor dysfunction caused by sudden pressure increases on the bladder. It occurs when sneezing, and is believed to be caused by a lack of support for the urethra and bladder neck. Most women suffer from this type of incontinence, and young women are more likely to experience it. The problem can be treated with pelvic floor muscle exercises like Kegels and physical therapy, according to [Dr David Gerber](#). There is also the option of minimally invasive surgery if other treatment options fail.

An overactive bladder is another common problem. It's characterized by urinating more than eight times in 24 hours and more than once at night. A number of dietary substances can affect bladder nerves, including caffeine, carbonated and/or alcoholic beverages, citrus, chocolate, and acidic or spicy foods. It is possible to treat overactive bladder through diet changes and bladder retraining. Modifying bladder function is intended to extend the time between trips to the bathroom. Dr David Gerber says you should control your bladder, not the other way around. Medications and second-line therapies such as Botox are also alternatives.

The third type of pelvic floor disorder is pelvic organ prolapse, which causes discomfort, problems with sexual activity, and bowel and bladder dysfunction. This type of dysfunction can be prevented by strengthening pelvic muscles, maintaining good bowel and bladder hygiene, and maintaining a healthy weight. The treatment options include doing nothing if the prolapse is not bothersome, inserting a pessary (a soft, removable device that supports the area affected by prolapse), or performing surgery.

It is very common to suffer from pelvic floor dysfunction, and it can severely impact your quality of life. Make an appointment with your doctor if you think you may have pelvic floor dysfunction. You can often get the best diagnosis and treatment plan from a subspecialist in Female Pelvic Medicine and Reconstructive Surgery.